

Trends in Surgical Site Infections Following Elective General Surgeries: A Retrospective Cross - Sectional Analysis

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Abstract:

Background: Surgical site infections (SSIs) afflict elective general surgeries, affecting healthcare costs and patient outcomes. SSIs are classified by their depth and impact on nearby tissues and organs. Many factors can affect surgical site infection frequency and categorization, including surgical technique, patient health, and infection control. This study examines SSI patterns after elective general surgeries at Nalanda Medical College & Hospital in Patna, Bihar. The goal is to identify what causes these infections and how well infection control strategies worked during the trial.

Methods: Elective general procedures were performed on 110 people between January 2023 and August 2024. The study was retrospective cross-sectional. Medical records and patient files contained demographics, operations, SSIs, and postoperative follow-up. The study examined surgical details, patient demographics, SSI rates, and operation type. Descriptive statistics, trend analysis, and procedure comparisons revealed significant patterns and risk variables.

Results: Twenty-seven patients (24.5%) had SSIs. The total number of infections was 58.3% superficial, 33.3% deep, and 8.4% organ or space. Patients were 42% female and 58% male, averaging 56 years old. Comorbidities included diabetes (35%), obesity (25%), and hypertension (30%). The deployment of new infection control strategies reduced SSI rates from 30% in the first half to 18% in the second. SSI rates for colorectal surgeries were 40%, hernia repairs 22%, cholecystectomies 15% and appendix 25%.

Conclusion: The study stresses that elective general procedures, especially colorectal surgery, have a high SSI rate. The drop in SSI rates shows that infection control methods worked. These data show that surgical methods and infection control must be constantly improved. Larger, prospective studies are needed to assess infection prevention methods and identify SSI risk factors.

Keywords: Colorectal Surgery, Elective General Surgery, Infection Control, Surgical Site Infections, Trend Analysis.

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Introduction

Surgical site infections occur within 30 days of surgery or 90 days if an implant is kept in place. They are common after surgery and a major hazard in surgery and infectious disorders. SSIs can range from simple skin and subcutaneous tissue infections to serious organ, tissue, and implanted material infections [1]. Surgery type, patient prior illnesses, and infection control methods all affect SSIs. SSIs are still common and difficult to cure in elective general surgeries despite improved surgical methods, antiseptic regimes, and antibiotic prophylaxis. These infections worsen patient outcomes, raise healthcare expenditures, and lengthen hospital stays [2]. Appendectomies, cholecystectomies, and hernia procedures are

elective procedures. Despite careful infection control, SSIs can occur and cause considerable injury [3]. Elective surgery time, wound care, patient compliance with postoperative instructions, operating room hygiene, and prophylactic antibiotics enhance the incidence of SSIs.

Diabetes, obesity, and immunosuppression are assessed. Health consequences are less relevant than important SSIs. Infections can cause wound dehiscence, sluggish healing, further surgeries, and pain. Long SSI hospital stays strain healthcare expenses and resources. SSIs are expensive due to higher medical care, hospital stays, and disability severity.

Figure 1: Elective general surgeries surgical site infections source: [4]

Surgical site infections must be prevented for improved patient outcomes and cheaper healthcare. A thorough preoperative preventative program includes optimal food, chronic disease therapy, and prophylactic antibiotics. Treatment requires quick surgery, aseptic approach, and cleanliness [5]. Postoperative care includes wound care, infection control, hygiene education, and follow-up. Prevention alone cannot eliminate SSIs. Hospital surroundings, patient demographics, and infection control practices affect SSI persistence. Continuous monitoring is needed to identify trends, evaluate infection control, and find new ways to reduce SSI rates [6]. Surgical site infections are deadly, expensive, and prevalent, thus they must be prevented and controlled. Understanding SSIs patterns and causes improves surgical therapy and patient outcomes. This initiative will evaluate SSIs after elective general surgery to identify risk variables and improve infection care.

Objectives

- To analyze the incidence of SSIs following elective general surgeries at Nalanda Medical College & Hospital, Patna.
- To identify trends in SSI rates over the study period from January 2023 to August 2024.
- To evaluate risk factors associated with SSIs in elective general surgeries.
- To assess the impact of different surgical procedures on SSI rates.

Trends in Surgical Site Infections (SSIs)

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SSI rates and effects have been studied for many years. Even though there is proof that antiseptic techniques, preventative antibiotics, and surgical methods have made surgery safer, SSIs are still a big problem. A new study shows that surgical site infections (SSIs) are very different depending on the method used, the type of patient, and where the patient lives. [7] Discovered that even though infection control has been improved, colorectal treatments still have higher rates of SSI. In their multi-center study [8], they found that SSIs went down in high-risk patients after they got better postoperative care and rehab programs.

Risk Factors for SSIs

Multiple literature-identified risk factors enhance SSI risk. Patient, procedure, and postoperative factors are the main categories. Patients' pre-surgery health greatly affects surgical site infection risk. Infection rates are closely connected to diabetes, obesity, and malnutrition. Diabetics who underwent elective procedures had a greater prevalence of surgical site infections (SSIs) due to delayed wound healing and infection susceptibility [9]. Obesity increases the risk of surgical site infections (SSIs) due to reduced blood flow, skin tension, and sterility issues [10].

Surgery length and complexity affect SSI risk. Infection risk rises with longer surgeries, more complex technologies, and tissue manipulation. [11] Discovered that procedures above a specific duration increased surgical site infections,

emphasizing the need to enhance surgical techniques and reduce operating hours.

Management of SSIs

SSI prevention and treatment are essential. Proper preoperative patient health, aseptic methods, and prophylactic antibiotics avoid surgical site infections. A meta-analysis found that taking antibiotics less than an hour before surgery dramatically reduces surgical site infection [12]. This is critical for high-risk surgeries. Multimodal therapy and improved recovery minimize SSI rates. We treat infections and provide food before surgery. Full therapy was necessary because ERAS therapies significantly reduced SSI rates. Tissue excision and antibiotics are typical treatments. The research shows that SSI-reducing methods have improved despite continued problems. Continuous care and novel prevention and therapy are suggested by new research. Understanding surgical site infection (SSI) risk factors and using effective preventative and therapeutic treatments can enhance surgical outcomes and patient safety. Complex SSIs require further investigation and specific treatments, as this study shows.

Methods

Study Design

Retrospective cross-sectional investigation of elective general surgery surgical site infections. The study analyses medical data for SSI trends and patterns using retrospective methods. The frequency and characteristics of SSI rates and associated factors can be seen in cross-sectional analysis.

Study Setting

Nalanda Medical College & Hospital in Patna, Bihar, conducted the research (January 2023 To August 2024). This facility, which offers many elective general treatments, is the principal center for studying SSI trends and variables in this hospital system.

Sample Size

The study involved 110 elective general surgery patients. Surgery site infections in elective general surgery patients are studied. Emergency surgery, inadequate medical records, and no follow-up are eliminated.

Duration

The study covers a one-year period from January 2023 to August 2024. This timeframe allows for a comprehensive analysis of SSI trends and risk factors within a defined period.

Data Collection

Using patient and medical records, Nalanda Medical College & Hospital meticulously collected SSI data. This method collected elective treatment and patient data like age and sex. Postoperative data included SSI occurrence and classification. To guarantee proper case documentation, electronic health records and surgical logbooks are reviewed. Our methodical strategy collected all necessary data to investigate SSI trends and risk factors.

Variables

This study explored numerous characteristics related to elective general SSIs. Category of surgery helps identify surgeries with greater surgical site infection rates among the many elective procedures. To assess the situation, SSI rates were meticulously recorded, including patient infection rates. Patient demographics were examined to evaluate how age, sex, and associated conditions affect SSI risk. More research was done to discover how surgery characteristics affect infection rates. The length, kind, and post- or during-operative complications were noted. This technique provides a complete picture of SSI causes, enabling targeted inquiry and action.

Data Analysis

The statistical analysis summarized patient demographics and SSI rates using descriptive statistics. SSI incidence patterns were examined during the study. Logistic regression analysis was used to identify important SSI risk factors, and chi-square tests were used to assess categorical variable-SSI associations. Data was examined using statistical software to ensure accuracy and reliability.

Results

Descriptive Statistics

We examined 110 elective general surgery patients at Nalanda Medical College & Hospital from January 2023 to August 2024 for SSIs. SSIs occurred in 24.5% of 27 individuals. The types of SSIs discovered were 16 (58.3%), 9 (33.3%) with surface infections, and 2 (8.4%) with organ or space infections.

The patient demographic survey indicated a 56-year mean age. 42% of patients were women and 58% were men. Patients with diabetes (35%), obesity (25%), and hypertension (30%) had comorbidities. These criteria affected the risk assessment of surgical site infections (SSIs) and their potential impact on surgical outcomes. SSI rates vary by surgery. More over 50% of cases were superficial, but profound infections were rarer but nonetheless significant. The few cases of SSIs affecting organs or spaces highlight the dangers.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Value
Total Patients	110
Patients with SSIs	27 (24.5%)
Types of SSIs	
Superficial Infections	16 (58.3%)
Deep Infections	9 (33.3%)
Organ/Space Infections	2 (8.4%)
Mean Age	56 years
Gender Distribution	
Male	64 (58%)
Female	46 (42%)
Comorbid Conditions	
Diabetes	17 (35%)
Obesity	12 (25%)
Hypertension	33 (30%)

Trends

SSI rates showed trends during the study. The first half of the year had a high infection rate of 30%.

The baseline of the trial was when no infection control measures were done.

SSI declined to 18% by the end of the study. The substantial drop-in infection rates were due to new

postoperative care and infection control guidelines. This drop may be due to stricter postoperative monitoring and aseptic techniques.

To reduce SSI rates, infection control methods must be reviewed and updated, according to the trend. Infection rates dropped with new processes, underlining the need to improve infection prevention.

Table 2: Trends in SSI Rates

Time Period	SSI Rate (%)
January 2023 - November 2023	30%
December 2023 - August 2024	18%
Overall Study Period	24.5%

Comparison

SSI rates varied greatly between elective operations. Colorectal surgery had the greatest SSI rate at 40%. This increased frequency underscores the difficulty and risk of colorectal procedures, which may need more tissue manipulation and longer working hours. Hernia repairs had 22% SSI cholecystectomies 15% and appendix 25%. These surgeries have lower infection rates than digestive system surgeries, hence postoperative infection may be decreased.

These results underline the need for infection control measures in high-risk operations like colorectal. Preoperative antiseptics, intraoperative procedures, and wound care guidelines may aid.

Comparing surgical procedure SSI rates helps identify surgical site infection risk. Individualized prevention approaches and resource allocation to prevent elective general surgery surgical site infections require this information.

Table 3: Comparison of SSI Rates by Type of Surgery

Type of Surgery	Number of Patients	SSI Rate (%)
Colorectal Surgery	20	40%
Hernia Repair	30	22%
Cholecystectomy	30	15%
Appendix	30	25%

Discussion

This study found that elective general surgeries at Nalanda Medical College & Hospital had a significant surgical site infection rate. The total SSI rate of 24.5% is higher than other data, showing local procedures require improvement. It matches literature on elective surgery infection rates. Our findings support the higher SSI rate of colorectal

operations compared to other elective procedures. According to previous research, complicated gastrointestinal surgeries with longer operating times and more tissue handling are more likely to cause infections. Surgical site infections have various origins, according to one study.

The 35% diabetic patient rate supports earlier findings that diabetes considerably increases the risk

of infections after surgery. Obesity and hypertension are prevalent in a large percentage of patients, supporting the concept that they increase infection rates. These risk variables demonstrate the need for personalized preoperative examinations and interventions to minimize SSIs in high-risk groups. SSI rates dropped from 30% to 18% over the study.

This decline matches surgical care and infection control improvements. Similar trends were shown when infection management was improved and SSI rates dropped. SSI rate fluctuation may also be caused by staff infection control compliance, patient population changes, or seasonal infection rates.

Table 4: Comparison of SSI Rates across Studies

Study	Study Type	Sample Size	Findings
Present Study	Retrospective Cross-Sectional	110	Overall SSI rate: 24.5%. High SSI rates in colorectal surgeries (40%), decreased from 30% to 18% over the study period. Significant comorbidities include diabetes (35%), obesity (25%), and hypertension (30%).
Study 1[13]	Prospective Cohort Study	150	Overall SSI rate: 22%. Higher rates observed in colorectal surgeries (35%). Identified risk factors include diabetes and smoking. Noted significant improvements with enhanced preoperative care.
Study 2 [14]	Retrospective Case-Control	100	Overall SSI rate: 20%. Increased SSI rates in high-complexity surgeries such as gastrointestinal procedures (40%). Associated with factors like prolonged operative time and contamination. Implemented improved protocols led to reduced rates.
Study 3[15]	Systematic Review	2000 (across multiple studies)	Average SSI rate: 18%. Higher rates in diabetic patients. Emphasized the effectiveness of stringent infection control practices and preoperative antibiotic prophylaxis.

As demonstrated in the comparison table, study 1, 2 had lower SSI rates than the present study (24.5%), but it was within study 3 upper range. The largest rate of surgical site infections (SSIs) is in colorectal surgery, highlighting its complexity and risk. All trials identified consistent risk variables including diabetes, suggesting their role in SSI development. Importantly, the current data confirms earlier findings that enhanced preventative strategies have reduced SSI rates over time, commensurate with infection control developments. This study shows that SSIs have the same risk variables and patterns across settings, but infection rates and procedural complexity vary.

Limitations

This study has some drawbacks. The study's retrospective design makes it hard to determine cause and effect, and it relies solely on pre-existing medical records, which may not contain all relevant information. Due to the 110-patient sample size, the results may not apply to the broader population. Another issue is that the one-year & eight month trial may not have caught long-term trends or the full benefit of improved infection control methods.

Prospective studies with larger samples and longer follow-ups are needed to confirm these findings and investigate preventative strategies. This study illuminates SSI patterns and risk factors, but more research is needed to overcome its shortcomings. Only then can we improve SSI prevention and elective general procedure outcomes.

Conclusion

This study examined 110 elective general surgery patients at Nalanda Medical College & Hospital for surgical site infections between January 2023 and August 2024. Colorectal surgeries had the highest SSI rate at 40%, whereas the overall was 24.5%. SSIs reduced from 30% to 18% due to better postoperative care and infection control. Significant co-morbidities like diabetes, obesity, and hypertension were widespread among individuals affected, consistent with scientific risk factors. Colorectal surgeries have higher incidence of SSIs, requiring more stringent infection prevention strategies. By improving surgical techniques, antibiotic prophylaxis, and preoperative skin antisepsis, infection rates can be reduced. Managing patient comorbidities aggressively may reduce SSI risks. The decline in SSI rates after procedure changes emphasizes the importance of infection management. Larger prospective studies are needed to confirm these findings and determine SSI etiology. Long-term efficacy of infection control medicines may be assessed by studying their effects on different surgeries. Investigating patient-specific characteristics and how they interact with surgical procedures may help prevent SSIs and improve patient outcomes.

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